

‘Charity Uncreated, Charity Created, and Charity Given’ ~
An Ontology of Divine Love in Julian of Norwich’s *Revelations*

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Introduction

The *Revelations of Divine Love* (“*Revelations*”) was written by anchoress Julian of Norwich (c.1342 – after 1416) (“Julian”) after 8 May 1373, when suffering grave illness, she was blessed with a series of sixteen apparitions and messages from God (“*showings*”).¹ These *showings* were centred around the Holy Trinity (who was hidden) and the Passion of Jesus Christ (which could be seen).² She completed her *Revelations* over her lifetime: a smaller version, written soon after the *showings*, and a longer, more ponderous text, written after many years of reflection on those *showings* (“LT”).³ It was not until 1670 that Julian’s *Revelations* was first printed.⁴ There has been much speculation and debate surrounding the practicalities and influences of her life, but no firm information exists of her earlier background, not even her name.⁵ It is known that after she wrote *Revelations*, she devoted the rest of her life to teaching and counselling on what she had learnt from her *showings* to her fellow Christians, in what could be termed ‘theological praxis’.⁶ This Paper will examine this theology, as it developed from Julian’s *showings*, considering alternative theology and orthodoxy, based on scripture, tradition, reasoning, and experience; however it will not provide a thorough biographical treatise on Julian’s life. Regarding her status as a theologian, it is assumed for the purposes of this Paper that she has borrowed from Neoplatonic concepts made available to her through other mystical theologians of the Middle Ages, but in any event, she has been called a ‘mystical theologian’ because she has received her insights directly from God, and not through rigorous systematic inquiry. This is a reason that her

¹ A. C. Spearing, “Introduction,” in Julian of Norwich *Revelations of Divine Love (Short Text and Long Text)*, trans. Elizabeth Spearing (London: Penguin Random House UK, 1998); Veronica May Wolf, *An Explorer’s Guide to Julian Norwich* (Illinois: IVP Academic, 2018) (e-book), Part One: Getting to Know Julian.

² Ibid. (both references).

³ Ibid. (both references).

⁴ Ann Lewin, *Love is the Meaning: Growing in Faith with Julian of Norwich* (Norwich: Canterbury Press, 2010) (e-book), Introduction.

⁵ Amy Frykholm, *Julian of Norwich* (Massachusetts: Paraclete Press, 2011) (e-book), Introduction.

⁶ Spearing, “Introduction”; Wolf, *An Explorer’s Guide*, Part One.

Revelations can be, at first glance, desultory (because of the seemingly random “pre-scholastic” order in which she reveals her theisms⁷); but on a closer examination of her LT, this Paper will demonstrate that Julian consistently develops an ontological understanding of Divine Love that is clearly the *centrepiece of*, and *reason for*, her theology. Julian provides her readers with a fresh understanding of church doctrines and orthodoxy through the incorporation of humanity into God, which is positively uplifting, radiating and accessible.⁸ Her theisms are briefly examined in this Paper, by utilizing the pivotal Chapter 84 of Julian’s LT as a hermeneutical framework to unmask the many hidden meanings and messages contained within her words.⁹ The framework utilized is a triad (closely reflecting the Holy Trinity), comprising three concepts of charity (or, alternatively, love): (1) Charity Uncreated – meaning God; (2) Charity Created – meaning the love created by God in the soul of humankind given back to him; and (3) Charity Given – meaning the virtue of loving. The crux of this triad is the relationship which God has *with* humankind. For Julian, it is the nature of the Trinity that is Divine Love, revealed in the Incarnation: the unity between God and all the souls of humankind. And the virtue of loving is the manifestation of God’s presence in humankind, reflecting the Divine Love of the Trinity. The third section of the Paper, Charity Given, will serve as a conclusion, firstly because it encapsulates the major principles of the first two sections, but mainly because it focusses on *how* humankind can practice what Julian preaches.¹⁰

⁷ Dom Cuthbert Butler, *Western Mysticism (2nd ed)* (London: Green & Co, 1919), 252.

⁸ Canon George Tolley, *Julian of Norwich: Saying ‘Yes’ to God* (Cambridge: Grove Books, 2010), 5.

⁹ See Walter Hilton, *The Scale of Perfection*, (ed. Evelyn Underhill) (John M. Watkins: London, 1948), 33, in support of this hermeneutical framework.

¹⁰ See Brant Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich: A Theological Reappraisal,” PhD diss., University of Edinburgh, 1976, 119 – 129, for a further reflection of this thematic structure.

Charity Uncreated

When Julian talks about “charity uncreated” in Chapter 84 of her LT, she is encompassing a theme that exists throughout her entire *Revelations*, and that is the extent to which Divine Love exists within God.¹¹ In so far as the doctrines of Revelation and Scripture are concerned, Julian provides knowledge of God that has been specifically and generally given to her.¹² Julian has apparitions of Christ on the Cross (in the presence of the Holy Trinity) and as such, she would be viewed as having ‘Special Revelation’, as well as the ‘General Revelation’ of God she had as a Christian, and more particularly, as an anchoress.¹³ This would have been through the lens of the Biblical narrative,¹⁴ but it is only clear that she is steeped in Biblical thought to the extent of the New Testament, and in particular, Pauline and Johannine writings.¹⁵ For instance, Julian’s portrayal of the *meaning* of God towards the end of her *Revelations* was clearly Johannine:¹⁶

... ‘Do you want to know what your Lord meant? Know well that love was what he meant. Who showed you this? Love. What did he show? Love. Why did he show it to you? For love...’¹⁷

The Apostle John teaches that “God’s purpose, Christ’s thirst, is for the bliss of all humanity”¹⁸ and “[his] words serve well to summarize Julian’s teaching on the love of God

¹¹ Tolley, *Julian of Norwich*, 14; see also Marilyn McCord Adams, “Julian of Norwich: Problems of Evil and the Seriousness of Sin,” *Philosophia* 39: no.3 (2011): 433-447 on a discussion regarding Julian’s concept of Divine Love.

¹² Beth Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine: An Introduction to Thinking and Living Theologically* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2014), 33 and 51.

¹³ Frykholm, *Julian of Norwich*, 7-8.

¹⁴ Robert W. Jenson, “Scripture’s Authority in the Church,” in *The Art of Reading Scripture*, ed. Ellen F. Davis and Richard B. Hays (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2003), 30; also see Matthew 16:24; Mark 8:34; Luke 9:23 and Philippians 3:10-11.

¹⁵ Sister Mary Paul, “Julian of Norwich and the Bible,” in *Julian of Norwich: Four Studies to Commemorate the Sixth Centenary of the Revelations of Divine Love* (Oxford: S.L.G. Press, 1973), 11.

¹⁶ See John 4:16-17

¹⁷ Julian of Norwich, *Revelations of Divine Love (Short Text and Long Text)*, trans. Elizabeth Spearing (London: Penguin Random House UK, 1998), Long Text, Chapter 86 [From here on the Chapter references from Julian of Norwich’s *Long Text* shall be referred to in the following manner: “LT86”]

¹⁸ Paul, “Julian of Norwich,” 11.

and his purpose to draw all [humans] to himself.”¹⁹ This theme directly leads to the *meaning* of the Trinity – which is the *meaning* of God. And in terms of Julian’s ontological examination and deliberations on Divine Love in her *Revelations*, Brant Pelphrey concisely states that:

The investigation of Julian’s theology which follows is arranged, therefore, after the three elements of Divine Love which Julian saw in her visions: of the Love which is God, the love which is given to us in Christ, and the experiences of love which is ours in Christ, as we are enabled to love by him.²⁰

This is a direct reflection of LT Chapter 84: Charity Uncreated, Charity Created and Charity Given. Much of the language used by Julian is trinitarian, often used as an analogy for the Trinity.²¹ It is as if the concept of the Trinity never leaves her mind, and even though she has sought *showings* (manifestations) of the Passion of the Christ (perhaps influenced by the ardent devotion to *imitatio Christi* that was common in her times²²), she was consistently aware of the Trinity in all of the *showings* that she was blessed with, and she made her devotion to the divine concept clear:

... For the Trinity is God, God is the Trinity; the Trinity is our maker and protector, the Trinity is our dear friend forever, our everlasting joy and bliss, through our Lord Jesus Christ. And this was shown in the first revelation, and in all of them; for it seems to me that where Jesus is spoken of, the Holy Trinity is to be understood...²³

¹⁹ Ibid., 11.

²⁰ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 124.

²¹ Ibid., 154.

²² Rolf, *An Explorer’s Guide*, (e-book), Part One: “Julian’s Three Gifts”.

²³ LT4.; Regarding the history and development of the Doctrine of the Trinity, this Paper relied on the following texts: Karl Barth, *Church Dogmatics, I.1: The Doctrine of the Word of God*, ed. and trans. G. W. Bromiley and T. F. Torrance (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1975), see 191, 193-194, and 296; and generally, Stephen R. Holmes, *The Quest for the Trinity: The Doctrine of God in Scripture, History and Modernity* (Illinois: IVP Academic, 2012); and Veli-Matti Kärkkäinen, *Christian Understandings of the Trinity: The Historical Trajectory* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017).

Many *versions* of the Trinity have been adopted and replaced by Christianity since the very first centuries, where God began to be understood more in doxological terms rather than by metaphysical approaches.²⁴ But Julian, in her plain vernacular (she was the first woman to write a substantial literary or religious work in English²⁵), and her pure understanding and devotion to God, was able to display a profound and sure-footed knowledge of the Doctrine of the Trinity, whilst arguably creating a refreshed theology of the concept (see further below). There were elements of Augustine’s *De Trinitate* in her thinking (she refers to God the Father of divine Power, God the Son as divine Wisdom, and the Holy Spirit as divine Love),²⁶ but it could also be said that it was Johannine in its simplicity.²⁷

As well as the Trinity, both Julian and Augustine carefully considered, both in a more recursive style, the Doctrine of *imago Dei*, and they understood its inextricable relevance to the Doctrine of the Trinity, but while Augustine’s orthodoxy was that “it is by virtue of our mind or inner self...that we are in the image of God[,]”²⁸ Julian’s depiction of God is in terms of human domestic kinship, care, and love: in fact she refers to the Motherhood of the Trinity, God, and Christ, and this will be discussed in the latter sections of this Paper.²⁹ Although Julian’s depictions were a departure from the intellectualist tradition of the Church at the time, and while she was branded as distempered and blasphemous by some, her *Revelations/showings* were never officially taken to be heretical.³⁰ In fact, over centuries, her expressed revelatory knowledge of God has been taken to be theological rather than merely

²⁴ Larry Hurtado, *Devotion to Jesus in Early Christianity* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2003), 42–53.

²⁵ Spearing, “Introduction,” vii.

²⁶ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 154.

²⁷ John 14:6-21.

²⁸ Janet Martin Soskice, “The Kindness of God: Trinity and the Image of God in Julian of Norwich and Augustine,” in Janet Martin Soskice, *The Kindness of God: Metaphor, Gender, and Religious Language* (e-book) (Oxford: Oxford Scholarship Online, 2011), 5/22.

²⁹ Lewin, *Love is the Meaning*, 1/14; And for alternative perspectives on *imago Dei*, this Paper considered Matthew R. Petrussek, *The Image of God and Moral Action: Challenging the Practicality of the Imago Dei* (Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, 2016).

³⁰ Soskice, “The Kindness of God,” 18/22 (Note 1).

mystical: “Theology begins with God’s revelatory word to us. It continues as we respond with words: words to God and words to each other.”³¹

Julian makes it clear throughout her *Revelations* that the Being of God is Love, but it is what she reveals about the Trinity that is most comforting and authentic. In reference to perichoresis, or Divine Indwelling of the Persons in one another (such that there are three Persons who are one Being), we are reminded by Julian that Charity Uncreated can only be seen through the Incarnate.³² But as mentioned above, the language that Julian uses to describe the perichoresis within the Trinity is warm, homely, and inviting – a derivation from orthodox interpretations and more so based on an intimate communion with humankind. For example, making one’s home with another, conveying the intimacy of a family, not only in the love between husband and wife, but between mother and child. Julian develops the concept of the perichoresis as an ontological approach to defining and characterising Divine Charity Uncreated through differing references to the Trinity: “Maker”, “Keeper”, “Lover”³³; “Truth”, “Wisdom”, Love³⁴; and “Fatherhood”, “Motherhood”, “Lordship”³⁵. For Julian, these convey the profound miracle of the Incarnation, which are directly based on Johannine principles of “divine indwelling”.³⁶ It is from this understanding of Charity Created that Julian derives her concept of atonement, “as an ontological relationship of God to [humankind] in Christ; and of the human response to God, in the indwelling of Christ in the soul, by the Holy Spirit, which mirrors the indwelling of the Persons of the Trinity in one another.”³⁷ This will be addressed in the next section of this Paper.

³¹ Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine*, 12.

³² LT22.; LT23.

³³ LT40.

³⁴ LT44.

³⁵ LT58.

³⁶ John 14 and 17.

³⁷ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 123.

Finally, although Julian is sure-footed in her descriptiveness and characterisations throughout her *Revelations*, she is acutely aware of the paradoxes of Charity Uncreated in the form of the Trinity – *hidden* and *known*. Although he is a God of divine “rest and peace”³⁸, there is a constant action in all that he has made.³⁹ This is known as ‘ecstasis’ and was particularly disclosed to her in LT Chapter 11. God is at the centre of the universe as eternal “Maker”, “Keeper”, and “Lover”.⁴⁰ Furthermore, Julian ponders on a God that cannot be seen even though she says she has seen God (in Christ) in her own *Revelations*. The answer to this paradox is in the “beholding” of Christ, who bears the likeness (or appearance) of God.⁴¹ Julian describes the *secrets* of an apophatic Trinity, i.e., the Being of God (the Indwelling Love of the Trinity as Father, Son and Holy Spirit), which is beyond humankind’s comprehension of *being* or *love*. But she reveals another *secret* as the Being of God towards humanity, which is the Love of the Son of God made human, who reveals the Trinity to humankind. This is Charity Created and is the embracement of humankind by God, and thus the ability of the embracement of God by humankind.⁴²

Charity Created

Julian discusses the concept of ‘theosis’ (to be Godified),⁴³ which is the mystical union uniting humankind with God. The process of ‘theosis’ is in the life of every Christian as they live in Christ and Christ lives in them – the bond between the Trinity and humanity.⁴⁴ She is concerned with the Indwelling of God in humankind – the communion of humankind and the Trinity, (uncreated) Love and (created) Love. This concerns two kinds of revelation:

³⁸ LT51.

³⁹ LT11.

⁴⁰ LT11., LT40; and see Anna Maria Reynolds, C. P., *Some Literary Influences in the Revelations of Julian of Norwich* (Leeds: Trinity and All Saints' Colleges, 1973).

⁴¹ LT43.

⁴² LT30.; LT34.

⁴³ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 185.

⁴⁴ LT54.

the discovery of the Trinity *of* humankind; and the discovery in the Trinity *in* humankind.⁴⁵ Julian says that the bond between the Trinity and humankind is so strong that their lives are absolutely incorporated in the life of Christ; and by the grace of God, humankind shares in the perichoresis of the Trinity: “God dwells in our soul.”⁴⁶

The second dimension of Julian’s ontology of Divine Love is therefore Charity Created: the created mirror of Charity Uncreated. It is the outpouring of (uncreated) Love into creation, in the act of creation itself, in the love which God has for what he has made, and in God’s constant work in creation, “keeping” what he has made in love: humankind’s souls in God and thus humanity being at one with the Trinity.⁴⁷ Julian sees a “hazelnut” as “all that is made” in creation⁴⁸, which “illustrates both the fragility and robustness of creation.”⁴⁹ God is therefore presented as a “maker”, who never takes his hands off his creation, as one would hold a little hazelnut in their palm, so as not to let it fall.⁵⁰

Julian pondered ‘the unity between God and humankind’s’ souls through Christ’, but her theisms on this topic *softened* existing Christological and soteriological viewpoints. Julian’s theisms were far more ‘joyful’ than medieval orthodoxy, and clearly more ‘joyful’ than the orthodoxy of today.⁵¹ In fact, a pertinent paradox in *Revelations* is that Julian understood a wondrous God of Love who had no wrath or anger, and she even extended that concept to *universal salvation*, but she was entangled with the real horrific suffering of

⁴⁵ LT56.

⁴⁶ Tolley, *Julian of Norwich*, 7.

⁴⁷ LT55.

⁴⁸ LT5.

⁴⁹ Tolley, *Julian of Norwich*, 10.

⁵⁰ Elaine Marie Biollo, “A God With Many Names: An Exploration of the Naming of God In Showings by Julian of Norwich,” PhD diss., Regis College and University of Toronto, 1999, 48

⁵¹ Marilyn McCord Adams, “Julian of Norwich: Problems of Evil and the Seriousness of Sin,” *Philosophia*, 39 (2011): 433.

Christ, and she wanted to suffer like him, and with him.⁵² But throughout her *showings* she only sees and feels Divine Love, regardless of the horrific circumstances.

Through her *showings*, Julian developed the concept of “oneing” (current editions of *Revelations* refer to “a joining” in its place⁵³), but from a literary perspective, the word directly translates to what is known as “atonement”, however the ontology of the concept could not be further from mainstream religious soteriological concepts of atonement.⁵⁴ Julian understands “oneing” with Christ as a reflection, or movement, of the Being of God into humankind - and the Charity Created, which she sees as a mirror of the Love of the Trinity, as seen in her *showings*.⁵⁵ The whole purpose of this is joy, and to share joy.⁵⁶ Atonement today conveys a joyless act, as a compelled reconciliation between sinful creation and an angry and mighty, masculine God.⁵⁷ Julian’s *showings* have great significance for contemporary human joy as she “challenged notions of God's vindictive remoteness with her understanding that indeed God has in Christ fully identified with us.”⁵⁸ Even through Christ’s suffering (as shown to her and felt by her), she maintains the concept of joy; because the “thirst” of Christ on the Cross, as referred to by the Apostle John (19:28), represents God’s *thirst for humanity*.⁵⁹

But there exists a paradox: the existence of the condition of evil and sin. Julian ponders on the question ‘if everything happens by the will of God, then what is sin?’⁶⁰ If our nature is to be *imago Dei*, why should sin be allowed?⁶¹ Julian, whilst disputing the existence

⁵² Tolley, *Julian of Norwich*, 8.

⁵³ LT53.

⁵⁴ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 190.

⁵⁵ LT23.; LT26.; LT31 – Refer to Julian of Norwich, *Showings*, trans. Edmund Colledge and James Walsh (Mahwah: Paulist Press, 1978) for original references to “oneing,”

⁵⁶ LT63.; LT24.; LT11.

⁵⁷ Kerry Dearborn, “The Crucified Christ as the Motherly God: The Theology of Julian of Norwich,” *Scottish Journal of Theology*, 55, no.3 (2002): 290.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*, 290.

⁵⁹ LT17.; LT31.; Paul, “Julian of Norwich,” 11.

⁶⁰ LT11.

⁶¹ LT27.

of sin, at times contemplates it as a necessary part of human existence, but says in any event that all things will be well.⁶² She reconciles this, to an extent, in LT Chapter 11, where she is given to understand that sin is a ‘non-thing’, or the absence of God. Towards the end of her *Revelations*, she understands that true human nature must be in the light of Christ (the ultimate model of humankind),⁶³ and anything contrary to his life is sin.⁶⁴ The capacity for humans to sin is to fail in “might”, “wisdom” and “goodness” (reflecting the Trinity) and is therefore to fail in being human,⁶⁵ but mercy exists.⁶⁶

The Mercy of God can be seen in Julian’s concept of the *sensual atonement* in Christ, and thus the movement of God into humankind. Christ is the “remaking” of human nature, which is necessary because of sin: “[T]here is a continual movement from Christ to the Trinity, and back again. In this sense, the humanity of Christ is a window for Julian which opens the way for her to understand, so far as she is able, his divinity. To see the Son of God, however, is to see the whole Trinity, and therefore the “homely” Love of God. Then, seeing the Trinity in Christ, Julian is drawn back to his humanity, and to her own relationship to God as a human being in his likeness.”⁶⁷ The greatest example of *sensual atonement* is seen in the crucifixion where Christ is Charity Created in the reflection of the Trinity.⁶⁸ Whereas the *atonement* of humankind occurs because, *despite* sin, Christ draws humankind to himself, as he dwells in the soul of the lover of God, and is loved and desired there, thereby continually *displacing* sin with his “homely” Love.⁶⁹ This can be seen in the ‘Parable of the Lord and Servant’⁷⁰ where Julian sees only a *fall and rise* of the servant who seeks to do good, and

⁶² LT35.; LT36.

⁶³ LT78.

⁶⁴ LT82.

⁶⁵ LT63.; LT27.

⁶⁶ Luke 23:34

⁶⁷ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 235; LT58.; LT62.; LT68.

⁶⁸ LT22.

⁶⁹ LT72.; LT81.

⁷⁰ LT51.

together with LT Chapter 59, it is clear that Julian's theme is *universal salvation*, for "the nature of God is to do good for evil."⁷¹

On the Christological aspects of *Revelations*, Julian does not merely present Christ as Mother as merely a feminist interpretation, but she does so to fulfill her belief in the totality of wonderment of God's grace.⁷² She utilises the metaphor of mother and child to highlight the undying and unconditional love God has for humankind.⁷³ Other medieval works placed all *onus* of the divine relationship on the sinner as a "weak wretch"⁷⁴, but it should be said that "the idea of the salvific role of Christ as Mother occurs in many schools of theological reflection in both Eastern and Western traditions."⁷⁵ Furthermore, whilst there is some debate, it is contended that Julian had been taught Augustinian theology. In fact, Augustine had created an ontological reality of divine feminine wisdom, created in Christ, which is reflected in his *Homily on Psalm 119*.⁷⁶ The nourishing and tenderness of a mother figure in this homily is amplified in *Revelations*, by reference to the Trinity, God, and the Saviour⁷⁷, as opposed to competing notions of "Christ's perfect maleness."⁷⁸ Denise Baker argues that the second Person of the Trinity 'binds' or 'knits' humankind's bodies with their souls, being wholly consistent with the medieval concept of 'women' being 'bodily' and 'sensual'. Julian

⁷¹ Cf. Adams, "Julian of Norwich," 439 – 441; Sarah McNamer, "The Exploratory Image: God as Mother in Julian of Norwich's Revelations of Divine Love," *Mystics Quarterly*, 15, no.1 (1989): 26; Paula S. Datsko Barker, "The Motherhood of God in Julian of Norwich's Theology," *The Downside Review*, last modified 8 June, 2022, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/001258068210034105/>, 298.

⁷² Tolley, "Julian of Norwich," 5; Barker, "The Motherhood of God," 290 – 304.

⁷³ McNamer, "The Exploratory Image," 24.

⁷⁴ LT8.; LT33.; LT34. See also Hilton, *The Scale of Perfection* and Anon., *The Cloud of Unknowing*, trans. Evelyn Underhill (New York: Global Grey Books, [c.1450]) (e-book)

⁷⁵ Kerry Hide, "The Deep Wisdom of Christ our Mother: Echoes in Augustine and Julian of Norwich," *The Australasian Catholic Record*, 74, no.4:432 (1997) 432; For a comprehensive list, refer to J. Heimmel, "God is Our Mother: Julian of Norwich and the Medieval Image of Feminine Divinity," *Elizabethan and Renaissance Studies*, 92, no.5 (1982), 1-33.

⁷⁶ St. Augustine, *On the Psalms*, trans. S. Hegbin and F. Corrigan (Westminster: Maryland, 1961), 20 – 21.

⁷⁷ LT74.; LT57.; LT52.; LT58.; LT59.; LT60.; LT61.

⁷⁸ Kari Elisabeth Borresen. "Matristics: Female Godlanguage in the Middle Ages," *Revue d'Histoire Ecclésiastique*, 95, no. 3 (2000): 343-62.

foretold this argument,⁷⁹ and hence why she can easily attribute homely and motherly attributes to Christ.⁸⁰

Charity Given – A Conclusion to *Revelations*

Because we mirror the Charity Uncreated in our own nature, we are able (by the mercy of God – the indwelling Son) to become ecstatic as God is ecstatic: to give love. Julian’s third great vision of love, therefore, is of “charity given”: the procession of love out of ourselves through the grace of God.⁸¹

Thus the third Person in the Holy Trinity is revealed, the Holy Spirit, because living in the work of the Holy Spirit is to be loving others with the Charity seen in God.⁸² Life is a "pilgrimage" or *transformation* in which Christ is the guide and source of life.⁸³ But the expression of Divine Love in humankind is by the “great and abundant grace” of the Holy Spirit.⁸⁴ For all our life is in three (reflecting the Holy Trinity): The first is nature (or kind⁸⁵), the second is mercy, and the third is grace (the manifestation of Christ in humankind’s lives).⁸⁶ Ann Lewin states that “Julian saw that God leads us by his Holy Spirit to desire mercy, and through contrition, compassion and true longing for God, restores us to wholeness.”⁸⁷ This is the point where Julian’s interacting *triad of charity* is bound. The sum of all three parts, and thereby all three Persons in perichoresis, is Divine Love. It is by way of Charity Given that humankind mirrors and expresses that love, including the love for God and all his creation (his “hazelnut”). For anchoress Julian, it was essential to fulfill this love through devotional and faithful prayer, meditation, and formal liturgy,⁸⁸ and she reassures

⁷⁹ LT56.

⁸⁰ Denise Nowakowski Baker, *Julian of Norwich's "Showings": From Vision to Book* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2014), 45.

⁸¹ Pelphrey, “Julian of Norwich,” 270.

⁸² *Ibid.*, 414.

⁸³ LT81.

⁸⁴ LT58.

⁸⁵ See Julian of Norwich, *Showings* (1978).

⁸⁶ LT58.

⁸⁷ Ann Lewin, *Love is the Meaning*, (e-book), Chapter 4.

⁸⁸ Liz McEvoy, *A Companion to Julian of Norwich* (Cambridge: D. S. Brewer, 2008) (e-book), Chapter 7.

that through such love, humankind's bond with the Trinity shall never be divided.⁸⁹ Julian experiences, and presents, a God of no wrath and anger, and by relaying God's message, "All shall be well"⁹⁰, humankind is not only presented with a *version* of God (who 'is positively *uplifting, radiating and accessible*'), but also One who provides the motherly love, compassion, empathy, acceptance, understanding, reconciliation, and forgiveness that was not only so very relevant (and comforting) in the difficult Middle Ages, but are at least equally (and even desperately) needed in the troubled times of today.⁹¹

⁸⁹ LT58.

⁹⁰ LT32.; Cf. Thomas Aquinas, *The Summa Theologica of St. Thomas Aquinas*, trans. Fathers of the English Dominican Province, vols. I and II (New York: Benziger Brothers, 1947).

⁹¹ A.M. Alchin, "Julian of Norwich for Today," in *Julian of Norwich: Four Studies to Commemorate the Sixth Centenary of the Revelations of Divine Love* (Oxford: S.L.G. Press, 1973), 36.

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